

Understanding the dairy beef production system in Atlantic Canada

University of Prince Edwards Island

CONSENT FORM

INVESTIGATORS

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DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCEDURES

If you select “Yes, I consent to be in this study”, it means you agree to participate in our study. You will be asked to complete an online survey (approximately 20 min in length). The questions are about basic herd information, farm and health management practices, challenges and motivations of dairy beef production, and herd production data.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO PARTICIPANTS AND SOCIETY

The data derived from this research may inform the participants and future work regarding how dairy-beef cattle are raised in Atlantic Canada and how the different stakeholders are connected through the production chain. Moreover, it will help the research team understand producer's motivations and challenges toward dairy-beef production as well as antibiotic use practices along the production chain. This knowledge will provide valuable information to improve the sustainability and security of dairy-beef production in Atlantic Canada.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

There are no known or anticipated risks and discomforts to your participation in this study.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

Your participation is voluntary. You can withdraw from the research project for any reason, at any time, without penalty. If you do not wish to participate, you do not have to provide any reason for your decision; however, the data collected to the point that you withdraw will still be used in the study. You are unable to withdraw from the research project after the results are aggregated, published, or presented. You should contact Thitiwich Changtes, Javier Sanchez, or Luke Heider with the contact information provided if you wish to withdraw from the research project.

FINANCIAL IMPLICATIONS

There will be no cost to you for participating in this study.

QUESTIONS

If you have any questions concerning the questionnaire and research project, please feel free to contact Thitiwich Changtes, Javier Sanchez, or Luke Heider at the contact information provided. This research project has been approved on ethical grounds by the University of Prince Edward Island.

PARTICIPANT CONSENT

Please read all the following statements

- A copy of letter of information has been provided and I had sufficient time to review it.
- The consent form has been provided and I had sufficient time to review it.
- I understand that I can keep a copy of the signed and dated consent form.
- I understand that I can withdraw at any time and not answer any question. However, data collected to the point you withdraw will be used in the study and may be published or presented.
- I understand that the information will be kept confidential within the limits of the law.
- No waiver of rights is sought.
- I understand that I can contact the UPEI Research Ethics Board at (902)-620-5104, or by email at researchcompliance@upei.ca if I have any concerns about the ethical conduct of this study.

*** 1. Please click “Yes” below, you consent to being part of this study:**

- Yes, I consent to be in this study.
- No

Reminder:

- Answer the following questions pertaining to **the current practices** on your farm.
- The person who answers the following questions should be **the decision maker for treatment and culling/selling** on your farm.
- **Definitions:**
 - **Surplus calves** – calves (bulls or heifers or dairy-beef), that are either unsuitable or not required to replace the milking herd (i.e., bull calves and non-replacement female calves).
 - **Bob/Bobby calves** – any dairy calves that are slaughtered at less than 3 weeks of age and 150 lbs.
 - **Veal calves** – any dairy calves that are marketed at ~20 weeks of age.
 - **Dairy beef steers/heifers** – any cattle with dairy genetics that are raised for beef rather than milk production and marketed at 12–14 months of age, including **purebred** Holsteins or dairy-beef **cross-bred** cattle.

2. Farm name

3. Contact information

Address _____

Tel. _____

Email _____

A. Farm characteristics

4. Where is your farm located?

- Prince Edward Island
- Nova Scotia
- New Brunswick
- Newfoundland and Labrador

5. Is your farm certified organic by the Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA)?

- Yes
- No

6. Are you using Dairy Herd Improvement (Lactanet) services?

- Yes
- No

7. What was average milk/cow/day (kilograms) in the last 12 months?

(Please enter a whole number)

8. How many lactating cows are in your herd today?

(Please enter a whole number)

9. What is the primary housing for lactating cows?

(Note: "**Primary housing**" is housing where lactating cows spend the majority of their time during the year)

- Tie stall
- Free stall
- Pole barn with bedded pack
- Other, please specify: _____

10. What is the predominant breed in your milking herd?

- Holstein
- Jersey
- Other (please specify) _____

11. What are the breeding practice(s) that you used in “replacement heifers” in the last 12 months?

(Please answer all the provided practices)

	Yes	No
a) Unsexed frozen dairy semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Unsexed frozen beef semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) Sexed frozen dairy semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Sexed frozen beef semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) Dairy bulls	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) Beef bulls	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
g) Dairy embryos	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
h) Beef embryos	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. What are the breeding practice(s) that you used in “milking cows” in the last 12 months?

(Please answer all the provided practices)

	Yes	No
i) Unsexed frozen dairy semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
j) Unsexed frozen beef semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
k) Sexed frozen dairy semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
l) Sexed frozen beef semen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
m) Dairy bulls	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
n) Beef bulls	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
o) Dairy embryos	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
p) Beef embryos	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. What proportion (%) of the herd is bred with beef semen?

(Enter "0" if you aren't using beef genetics in your herd)

14. What are the top 3 beef breeds you are using for beef semen?

(Please **specify** and **rank** according to the frequency **in the last 12 months**, where 1 = the most frequent, or enter "-" if are **not using any beef semen**)

1st Breed _____
 2nd Breed _____
 3rd Breed _____

B. Producer background information

15. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to say

16. What is your age?

- Under 30 years old
- 30 – 39 years old
- 40 – 49 years old
- 50 – 59 years old
- 60 years old or older
- Prefer not to say

17. What is the highest degree or level of schooling you have completed?

(If currently enrolled, highest degree received.)

- Primary, middle, or high school
- Post-secondary education (i.e., college or university)
- Postgraduate education (i.e., doctorate or master's degrees)
- Prefer not to say
- Other (please specify) _____

18. How many years have you been dairy farming (years)?

(Please enter a whole number, or enter "999" if prefer not to say)

19. Does the farm owner work off the farm in addition to dairy farming?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

C. The stakeholders and the dairy beef production chain in Atlantic Canada

Definitions:

- **Surplus calves** – calves (bulls or heifers or dairy-beef), that are either unsuitable or not required to replace the milking herd (i.e., bull calves and non-replacement female calves).

20. Do you euthanize any newborn surplus calves immediately?

- Yes
- No

**C. The stakeholders and the dairy beef production chain in Atlantic Canada
(Pre-weaned surplus calves)**

***21. Do you raise and sell any surplus calves as pre-weaned calves?**

- Yes **(Go to question 22)**
- No **(Go to question 35)**

22. How many pre-weaned surplus calves have you sold in the last 12 months (calves)?
(Please enter a whole number)

23. What are your common practices for selling your pre-weaned surplus calves?

(Please select all that apply)

- Sell them directly to a **slaughterhouse** as bob/bobby calves
- Sell them directly to a **nursery/calf rearer**
- Sell them directly to a **veal farm**
- Sell them directly to a **feedlot**
- Sell them to an **auction/livestock market/selling yard**
- Sell them to a **third party agent**, such as drover
- Sell them directly to a **dairy farm**
- Other (please specify) _____

24. What is the most frequent practice for selling your pre-weaned surplus calves?

(Please answer this question by using the drop-down box)

	Sell them directly to a slaughterhouse as bob/bobby calves
	Sell them directly to a nursery/calf rearer
	Sell them directly to a veal farm
	Sell them directly to a feedlot
	Sell them to an auction/livestock market/selling yard
	Sell them to a third party agent , such as drover
	Sell them directly to a dairy farm
	Other

25. Indicate the approximate weight (lbs) of the pre-weaned surplus calves when they are sold according to the most frequent practice indicated in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number)

26. Indicate the age of the pre-weaned surplus calves when they are sold according to the most frequent practice indicated in the previous question:

- < 1 week
- 1 - 2 weeks
- 3 – 4 weeks
- > 4 weeks

D. Dairy producer's motivations and challenges toward dairy beef production in Atlantic Canada

(Pre-weaned surplus calves)

27. If you raise and sell any surplus calves as pre-weaned calves, please indicate the reasons for doing so according to:

(Please answer all statements)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I don't know what to do with surplus calves.					
Our veterinarian advised us to sell our pre-surplus calves.					
I have limited labor capacity to keep surplus calves on my farm.					
I have limited housing and land capacity to house surplus calves on my farm.					
I have limited feed supply or stock for surplus calves on my farm.					
I produce few surplus calves on my farm.					
I sell surplus calves to maintain herd size due to limited milk quota.					
I have a limited budget to keep surplus calves on my farm.					
I sell surplus calves to reduce production costs.					
I sell surplus calves because I cannot earn a profit from them.					
I sell surplus calves because there is a low demand of dairy beef products on the market.					
I sell surplus calves because I want immediate profits from them.					
Surplus calves have poor survival chances when kept on farm.					

Other reasons why you sold surplus calves as pre-weaned calves (please specify)

**E. Antibiotic use in surplus calves on dairy farms
(Pre-weaned surplus calves)**

28. Do you feed any “milk/milk replacer containing antibiotic” or “mastitic milk” or “waste milk” to your pre-weaned surplus calves?

- Yes
- No

29. Do you follow veterinary treatment protocols when treating pre-weaned surplus calves?

- Yes, always
- Yes, sometimes
- No

30. What are the top 3 antibiotics used for treating pre-weaned surplus calves on your dairy farm?

(Please **specify** and **rank** according to the frequency **in the last 12 months**, where 1 = the most frequent)

- 1st Commercial name _____
- 2nd Commercial name _____
- 3rd Commercial name _____

31. Indicate the reasons for treating your pre-weaned surplus calves with antibiotics:

(Please select all that apply)

- Failure of Transfer of Passive Immunity (FTPI)
- Pneumonia/Respiratory diseases
- Diarrhea
- Navel infections/Omphalitis
- Abnormal joint
- Lameness
- Metabolic Disease
- Other (please specify) _____

32. What is the most frequent reason for treating your pre-weaned surplus calves with antibiotic?

(Please answer this question by using the drop-down box)

	Failure of Transfer of Passive Immunity (FTPI)
	Pneumonia/Respiratory diseases
	Diarrhea
	Navel infections/Omphalitis
	Abnormal joint
	Lameness
	Metabolic Disease
	Other

33. Do you use antibiotics in any healthy pre-weaned surplus calves (no symptoms or clinical signs) for disease prevention and control?

- Yes
- No

34. Has your herd veterinarian detected any antibiotic resistant infections in your pre-weaned surplus calves?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

**C. The stakeholders and the dairy beef production chain in Atlantic Canada
(Weaned surplus calves)**

***35. Do you raise and sell any surplus calves as weaned calves?**

- Yes **(Go to question 36)**
- No **(Go to question 49)**

36. How many weaned surplus calves have you sold in the last 12 months(calves)?
(Please enter a whole number)

37. What are your common practices for selling your weaned surplus calves?

(Please select all that apply)

- Sell them directly to a **slaughterhouse** as bob/bobby calves
- Sell them directly to a **nursery/calf rearer**
- Sell them directly to a **veal farm**
- Sell them directly to a **feedlot**
- Sell them to an **auction/livestock market/selling yard**
- Sell them to a **third party agent**, such as drover
- Sell them directly to a **dairy farm**
- Other (please specify) _____

38. What is the most frequent practice for selling your weaned surplus calves?

(Please answer this question by using the drop-down box)

	Sell them directly to a slaughterhouse as bob/bobby calves
	Sell them directly to a nursery/calf rearer
	Sell them directly to a veal farm
	Sell them directly to a feedlot
	Sell them to an auction/livestock market/selling yard
	Sell them to a third party agent , such as drover
	Sell them directly to a dairy farm
	Other

39. Indicate the average weight (lbs) of the weaned surplus calves they are sold according to the most frequent practice indicated in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number)

40. Indicate the average age (weeks) of the weaned surplus calves when they are sold according to the most frequent practice indicated in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number)

D. Dairy producer's motivations and challenges toward dairy beef production in Atlantic Canada
(Pre-weaned surplus calves)

41. If you raise and sell any surplus calves as weaned calves, please indicate the reasons for doing so according to:

(Please answer all statements)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I don't know what to do with surplus calves.					
Our veterinarian advised us to sell our surplus calves.					
I have limited labor capacity to keep surplus calves on my farm.					
I have limited housing and land capacity to house surplus calves on my farm.					
I have limited feed supply or stock for surplus calves on my farm.					
I produce few surplus calves on my farm.					
I sell surplus calves to maintain herd size due to limited milk quota.					
I have a limited budget to keep surplus calves on my farm.					
I sell surplus calves to reduce production costs.					
I sell surplus calves because I cannot earn a profit from them.					
I sell surplus calves because there is a low demand of dairy beef products on the market.					
I sell surplus calves because I want immediate profits from them.					
Surplus calves have poor survival chances when kept on farm.					

Other reasons why you sold surplus calves as weaned calves (please specify)

**E. Antibiotic use in surplus calves on dairy farms
(Weaned surplus calves)**

42. Do you feed any “milk/milk replacer containing antibiotic” or “mastitic milk” or “waste milk” to your weaned surplus calves before weaning?

- Yes
- No

43. Do you follow veterinary treatment protocols when treating weaned surplus calves?

- Yes, always
- Yes, sometimes
- No

44. What are the top 3 antibiotics used for treating weaned surplus calves on your dairy farm?

(Please **specify** and **rank** according to the frequency **in the last 12 months**, where 1 = the most frequent)

1st Commercial name _____

2nd Commercial name _____

3rd Commercial name _____

45. Indicate the reasons for treating your weaned surplus calves with antibiotics:

(Please select all that apply)

- Failure of Transfer of Passive Immunity (FTPI)
- Pneumonia/Respiratory diseases
- Diarrhea
- Navel infections/Omphalitis
- Abnormal joint
- Lameness
- Metabolic Disease
- Other (please specify) _____

46. What is the most frequent reason for treating your weaned surplus calves with antibiotic?

(Please answer this question by using the drop-down box)

	Failure of Transfer of Passive Immunity (FTPI)
	Pneumonia/Respiratory diseases
	Diarrhea
	Navel infections/Omphalitis
	Abnormal joint
	Lameness
	Metabolic Disease
	Other

47. Do you use antibiotics in any healthy weaned surplus calves (no symptoms or clinical signs) for disease prevention and control?

Yes

No

48. Has your herd veterinarian detected any antibiotic resistant infections in your weaned surplus calves?

Yes

No

Don't know

**C. The stakeholders and the dairy beef production chain in Atlantic Canada
(Finished veal calves)**

Definitions:

- Veal calves – any dairy calves that are marketed for beef at ~ 20 weeks of age.

***49. Do you raise and sell surplus calves as finished veal calves?**

- Yes **(Go to question 50)**
- No **(Go to question 56)**

50. How many finished veal calves have you sold in the last 12 months (calves)?
(Please enter a whole number)

51. What are your common practices for selling your finished veal calves?

(Please select all that apply)

- Sell them directly to a **slaughterhouse**
- Sell them to an **auction/livestock market/selling yard**
- Sell them to a **third party agent**, such as a drover
- Other (please specify) _____

52. What is the most frequent practice for selling your finished veal calves?

(Please answer this question by using the drop-down box)

	Sell them directly to a slaughterhouse as bob/bobby calves
	Sell them to an auction/livestock market/selling yard
	Sell them to a third party agent , such as drover
	Other

53. Indicate the average weight (lbs) of the finished veal calves when they are sold according to the most frequent practice in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number)

54. Indicate the average age (weeks) of the finished veal calves when they are sold according to the most frequent practice in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number) (1 month = 4 weeks)

D. Dairy producer's motivations and challenges toward dairy beef production in Atlantic Canada

55. If you raise and sell surplus calves as finished veal calves, please indicate the reasons for doing so according to:

(Please answer all statements)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I have knowledge and understand about raising veal calves.					
I have learned about raising veal calves from other veal producers.					
Our veterinarian advised us to produce veal calves.					
I have my own veal farm/nursery.					
I produce a lot of surplus calves on my farm.					
I raise surplus calves for veal calves to maintain herd size due to limited milk quota.					
I cannot transport or sell surplus calves at 8 days of age or less.					
I cannot transport surplus calves for more than 12 hours.					
The government supports me raising veal calves.					
I can earn more profit from surplus calves by raising them as veal calves rather than selling them at a younger age.					
I raise veal calves because there is a high demand for veal products on the market					
I raise veal calves because the price for veal animals is high					
I raise veal calves to maximize the use of labor on my farm					
I raise veal calves to maximize the use of barns and land capacity on my farm					
I raise veal calves to maximize the use of feed					

Other reasons why you sold surplus calves as finished veal calves (please specify)

**C. The stakeholders and the dairy beef production chain in Atlantic Canada
(Finished steers/heifers)**

Definition:

- **Dairy beef steers/heifers** – any cattle with dairy genetics that are raised for beef rather than milk production and marketed at 12–14 months of age, including **purebred** Holsteins or dairy-beef **cross-bred** cattle.

***56. Do you raise and sell surplus calves as finished steers/heifers?**

- Yes **(Go to question 56)**
- No **(Go to question 63)**

57. How many finished steers/heifers cattle have you sold in the last 12 months?
(Please enter a whole number)

58. What are your common practices for selling your finished steers/heifers?
(Please select all that apply)

- Sell them directly to a **slaughterhouse**
- Sell them to an **auction/livestock market/selling yard**
- Sell them to a **third party agent** such as drover
- Other (please specify) _____

59. What is the most frequent practice for selling your finished steers/heifers?
(Please answer this question by using the drop-down box)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Sell them directly to a slaughterhouse as bob/bobby calves
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sell them to an auction/livestock market/selling yard
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sell them to a third party agent , such as drover
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other

60. Indicate the average weight (lbs.) of the finished steers/heifers when they are sold according to the most frequent practice indicated in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number)

61. Indicate the average age (months) of the finished steers/heifers when they are sold according to the most frequent practice indicated in the previous question:

(Please enter a whole number)

**D. Dairy producer's motivations and challenges toward dairy beef production in Atlantic Canada
(Finished steers/heifers)**

62. If you raise and sell surplus calves as finished steers/heifers, please indicate the reasons for doing so according to:

(Please answer all statements)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I have knowledge and understand about raising dairy beef steers/heifers.					
I have learned about raising dairy beef steers/heifers from other dairy-beef producers.					
Our veterinarian advised us to produce dairy beef steers/heifers.					
I have my own feedlot/nursery.					
I produce a lot of surplus calves on my farm					
I raise surplus calves for dairy beef steers/heifers to maintain herd size due to limited milk quota.					
I cannot transport or sell surplus calves at 8 days of age or less.					
I cannot transport surplus calves for more than 12 hours.					
The government supports me raising dairy beef steers/heifers.					
I can earn more profit from surplus calves by raising them as dairy beef steers/heifers rather than selling them at a younger age					
I raise dairy beef steers/heifers because there is a high demand for beef products on the market					
I raise dairy beef steers/heifers because the price for dairy beef animals is high					
I raise dairy beef steers/heifers to maximize the use of labor on my farm					
I raise dairy beef steers/heifers to maximize the use of barns and land capacity on my farm					
I raise dairy beef steers/heifers to maximize the use of feed.					

Other reasons why you sold surplus calves as finished steers/heifers (please specify)

Thank you for your time and information for our study!

If you have any questions, please contact Dr. Thitiwich Changtes (tchangtes@upei.ca; 902-916-5153), Dr. Javier Sanchez (jsanchez@upei.ca; 902-566-0803), or Dr. Luke Heider (lcheider@upei.ca; 902-566-0661). If you have any concerns about how the research was done, please contact the UPEI Research Ethics Board at researchcompliance@upei.ca or 902-620-5104.

Once all parts of the study are complete, the researchers may share the findings via producer meetings, scientific journals, or social media platforms.

***63. May we contact you for further information as part of this or similar studies, understanding that you can always choose not to participate further at that time?**

- Yes
- No